

Financial Performance Analysis: A Case Study of Bandhan Bank

Dr. Sanjay Dawn

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Naba Ballygunge Mahavidyalaya, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

Banking industry plays a very important role for sustainable economic progress in a developing nation like India. Bandhan Bank plays a crucial role in reaching out to the marginalized people from remote areas of the Country for this economic progress. Although Bandhan's journey spans over two decades, it has accumulated only a short experience as a bank. Now, Bandhan bank's entire performance is directly impacted by the increase of non-performing assets. The current study is analytical in nature and is entirely dependent on secondary data that has been examined utilizing accounting and statistical tools. The Bandhan Bank was founded few years ago and running profitably, but currently the bank is facing several problems due to NPAs. In light of the aforementioned context, the current study examines the trend of NPA in Bandhan Bank and evaluates the performance of Bandhan Bank with reference to the terrible problem of Non-Performing Asset.

KEYWORDS: Non-Performing Asset, Financial Inclusion, Bandhan Bank, Women Empowerment

I. INTRODUCTION

The banking system plays an important role in accelerating the overall development of the country by ensuring financial inclusion to all marginalized people of a country. Bandhan Bank was also quietly playing an important role in the overall development of the marginalized people, small businesses, agriculture and other small scale industries in the Indian economy. 'Bandhan' started its journey in 2001 as a society for financial inclusion and women's empowerment in rural areas of West Bengal through sustainable livelihood creation followed by microfinance activities. In 2010 'Bandhan' became India's largest microfinance institution (MFI). It made its debut on 23rd August 2015 as a universal bank from an NGO, aiming to provide last mile banking to all, big or small, from unbanked and under reached areas by the philosophy of 'Your benefit. Everyone's welfare'.

Although Bandhan Bank emerged and performed successfully in the early stage of their incorporation, but now it experienced some unwanted difficulties. The main reason for the dismal performance of Bandhan Bank is that most of the assets are non-performing and overdue increase over the period. Now, non-performing assets are a pressing problem

How to cite this paper: Dr. Sanjay Dawn "Financial Performance Analysis: A Case Study of Bandhan Bank" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-7 | Issue-5, October 2023, pp.1031-1035, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd60018.pdf

Copyright © 2023 by author (s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

for most of the banks. In such a situation considering the NPA, it is very important to consider the financial health and performance of Bandhan Bank.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Basu, S., Dutta, S., and Sarkar, A. (2015), in their article they exhibits that Bandhan Bank entered the banking sector with a 99.5% success rate in micro lending at a time when other banks were finding it difficult to cut back on problematic loans. It has found that Bandhan works well in situations where customers have no alternative means of obtaining money. As a commercial bank, it will be difficult to serve a variety of clients while maintaining the current level of non-performing assets (NPA) by ongoing oversight of bad loans, which will ultimately prove to be an expensive endeavour.

Thomas, S. and Dave, G.B. (2015), in their study explore that Bandhan become a more organized banking institution and people obtain more loans from this bank. They also examined the financial structure of the organization as both an NBFC and an NGO. Its financial structure as an NBFC and an NGO is highlighted in the first half of the report. The study goes on to analyze the finance structure during the previous five years.

Mustafa, M. S. M. and Taqi, M. (2017), in their study examine the profitability position and business performance of Punjab National Bank as well as measures the impact of deposits and advances on the profitability of the bank using various financial ratios based on secondary data. They found the bank has performed well on the sources of growth rate and financial efficiency but profitability position has been found poor during the study period.

Nayak, S. (2017), in her article disclose that how the private sector has played its role in achieving financial inclusion and try to find out the sustainability of Bandhan Bank in the long run using SWOC analysis based on secondary sources of data.

Agarwal, R. (2019), in his research paper evaluate the financial performance and soundness of nineteen selected nationalized banks in India using CAMEL model. This study reveals the performance using twelve financial ratios of the parameters of capital adequacy, assets quality, management efficiency, earnings and liquidity. In this study he found that Indian bank stood at top in respect of capital adequacy, management and earning efficiency.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the study are

- To examine the trend of NPA in Bandhan Bank
- To evaluate the performance of Bandhan Bank with reference to the terrible problem of Non-Performing Asset

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data Collection: The data has been collected from secondary source which includes RBI reports, various articles, journals, research papers and various websites.

Period of the Study: The present study has been covered a period of 2015-16 to 2022-23 to compare and analyze the data.

Tools and Techniques: The data are analyzed by utilizing different accounting and statistical tools and conceptual understanding.

V. ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE OF BANDHAN BANK WITH REFERENCE TO NPA

Non-performing Asset is one of the most crucial factors in analyzing the bank's financial performance. In this section assessed financial standing of the Bandhan Bank. The quality of the bank's credit portfolio is indicated by gross NPA. It is illustrated in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Net NPA Ratio and Gross NPA Ratio of Bandhan Bank

Year	Gross NPAs (Rs. In Core)	Gross NPA Ratio (%)	Net NPAs (Rs. In Core)	Net NPA Ratio (%)
2015-16	18.77	0.15	10.24	0.08
2016-17	86.26	0.51	61.17	0.36
2017-18	373.14	1.25	172.90	0.58
2018-19	819.56	2.04	228.32	0.58
2019-20	992.78	1.48	389.40	0.58
2020-21	5757.76	6.81	2861.03	3.51
2021-22	6380.00	6.46	1564.23	1.66
2022-23	5298.62	4.87	1228.27	1.17
Average		2.95		1.06
SD		2.68		1.10

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of the Bandhan Bank

A high Gross NPA ratio indicates poor quality of loan portfolio. Table 1 indicates that over the research period i.e. 2015-16 to 2022-23, the average Gross Non-Performing Asset (NPA) was 2.95% and illustrates that the Gross NPA ratio of Bandhan Bank disproportionately increased from 2015-16 to 2022-23. Bandhan Bank's Gross NPA Ratio climbed from 0.15% to 4.87% which shows a consistent upward trend. The Standard Deviation of Gross NPA ratio is 2.68%. It indicates that the Bandhan Bank management is not giving enough attention to maintaining and adhering to ideal standards when providing advances, which results in an unsatisfactory recovery and a greater Gross NPA ratio.

The bank's current loan risk is shown by Net NPA. High Net NPA Ratio implies the existence of highly hazardous loans of the bank for which no suitable provision has been made. The Average Net NPA Ratio of Bandhan Bank is 1.06% and the Standard Deviation of Net NPA Ratio is 1.10%. Net NPA Ratio of Bandhan Bank also shows the increasing trend over the period from 2015-16 to 2022-23. Net NPA Ratio of Bandhan

Bank increased from 0.08% to 1.17% except the year 2020-21 and 2021-22. In these two years NPAs increased as recovery was not satisfactorily possible due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

Table 2: Sector-wise classification of NPAs of Bandhan Bank

Year	Priority Sector NPAs		Non- Priority Sector NPAs		Total NPAs Rs. in Crore
	Rs. in Crore	Percentage (%)	Rs. in Crore	Percentage (%)	
2015-16	18.56	98.88	0.21	1.12	18.77
2016-17	85.89	99.57	0.37	0.43	86.26
2017-18	363.84	97.51	9.30	2.49	373.14
2018-19	399.85	48.91	417.71	51.09	817.56
2019-20	481.83	48.53	510.95	51.47	992.78
2020-21	4999.47	86.83	758.29	13.17	5757.76
2021-22	2763.74	43.32	3616.26	56.68	6380.00
2022-23	2073.57	39.13	3225.05	60.87	5298.62
Correlation (r)	0.887		0.836		
r = Coefficient of Correlation between the amounts of different sectors to the total amounts					

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of the Bandhan Bank

Bandhan Bank divided its entire Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) into two groups i.e. the Priority Sector and the Non-Priority Sector. Table 2 displays Bandhan Bank's NPAs for the eight years from 2015-16 to 2022-23. It shows that the proportion of Bandhan Bank's total Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) in the Priority Sector has dramatically dropped, from 98.88% in 2015-16 to 39.13% in 2022-23. From 2015-16 to 2022-23, the Non-Priority Sector's share of Total NPAs climbed dramatically from 1.12% to 60.87%. There is a strong degree of positive correlation between Priority Sector NPAs and Total NPAs, as indicated by the correlation coefficient of 0.887. This result shows that there has been a comparable increase in Total NPAs with a rise in Priority Sector NPAs. Once more, there is a very strong positive correlation between Non-Priority Sector NPAs and Total NPAs, which was indicated by the correlation of 0.836 between the two variables. This result also shows that there has been a comparable increase in Total NPAs with a rise in NPAs in the Non-Priority Sector.

Table 3: Correlation between Net Profit and Net NPA of Bandhan Bank

Year	Net NPAs (Rs. In Core)	Net Profit (Rs. In Core)
2015-16	10.24	275.25
2016-17	61.17	1111.95
2017-18	172.90	1345.56
2018-19	228.32	1951.50
2019-20	389.40	3023.74
2020-21	2861.03	2205.46
2021-22	1564.23	2257.94
2022-23	1228.27	2194.64
Correlation (r)	0.462	

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of the Bandhan Bank

Table 3 explore that the correlation between Net Profit and Net NPA is 0.462, which indicates that there is a moderate degree of positive correlation between Net Profit and Net NPA. This illustrates that the Net NPA is consistently increasing with the subsequently increase in Net Profit. This is not satisfactory for any bank as it adversely affects the profitability and financial health of the bank.

VI. ANALYSIS OF THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF BANDHAN BANK

To analyze the financial performance of Bandhan Bank all the parameters used in ratio based CAMEL model i.e. Capita Adequacy, Assets Quality, Management Competency, Earnings Efficiency and Liquidity Position have been considered. Here an attempt has been made to analyze the financial performance of Bandhan Bank with the help of some important ratios as follows:

Table 4: Financial Performance of Bandhan Bank

Year	Capital Adequacy	Asset Quality		Management Competency		Earnings Efficiency		Liquidity Position	
	Capital Adequacy Ratio (%)	Net NPA to Net Advance (%)	Net NPAs to Total Assets (%)	ROE (%)	Profit Per employee (Rs. in Crore)	NIM (%)	ROA (%)	Current Ratio (%)	Quick Ratio (%)
2015-16	29.01	0.08	0.05	16.00	0.01	11.04	1.88	0.01	10.45
2016-17	26.36	0.36	0.20	28.51	0.05	10.44	4.46	0.01	15.09
2017-18	31.48	0.58	0.39	25.98	0.05	9.69	4.03	0.01	42.66
2018-19	29.20	0.58	0.40	19.00	0.06	10.43	4.25	0.01	29.69
2019-20	27.43	0.58	0.42	21.07	0.08	8.12	4.18	0.02	24.17
2020-21	23.47	3.51	2.49	13.24	0.05	7.78	2.13	0.02	33.33
2021-22	20.10	1.66	1.13	0.76	0.002	8.17	0.10	0.06	20.03
2022-23	19.76	1.17	0.79	11.80	0.034	7.21	1.50	0.09	35.71
Mean	25.85	1.065	0.73	17.04	0.04	9.11	2.81	0.028	26.391
SD	4.33	1.10	0.78	8.78	0.03	1.45	1.62	0.03	10.94

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of the Bandhan Bank

Capital Adequacy Ratio is very important to analyze the capital structure as it is necessary and important to maintain the confidence of all the investors and save the bank from bankruptcy. Table 4 shows that Capital Adequacy Ratio of the bank significantly decreasing over the period of the study i.e. from 29.01% to 19.76%. It is quite alarming of the bank's financial health and stability.

Assets Quality Ratio indicates the quality of loans of the bank which are given to earn interest income. Table 4 shows that both the ratio i.e. Net NPA to Net Advance and Net NPAs to Total Assets are significantly disproportionately increase during the period 2015-16 to 2022-23. The Net NPA to Net Advance of the bank from 0.08% to 1.17% and Net NPAs to Total Assets of the bank from 0.05% to 0.79%. It indicates the assets quality of Bandhan Bank has not been improving during the period of 2015-16 to 2022-23 which is reflected in the disproportionately increasing trend of assets quality ratio.

The performance management competency of the banking unit is measured in terms of certain ratio like Return on Equity/Net worth (ROE), Profit per employee etc. which helps the management to add value to the stakeholders and play crucial role in making strategic decision. By using this ratio from the Table 4, it is observed that ROE and Profit per employee both the indicators are very fluctuating and disproportionately decreased over the period 2015-16 to 2022-23.

The important two ratios i.e. Net Interest Margin (NIM) and Return on Assets (ROA) are used to measure the earning efficiency. NIM is considered a

significant profitability indicator for evaluating the effectiveness and stability of the bank. Table 4 shows that NIM is significantly disproportionately decreasing trend from 11.04% in 2015-16 to 7.21% in 2022-23. Again, ROA is a profitability ratio which helps evaluate how the bank efficiently used its assets. Table 4 also shows that ROA of the Bandhan Bank significantly disproportionately decreasing over the period which indicates Bank's performance is deteriorating.

Liquidity position is also important parameters to analysis the financial performance of the bank as it allow the investors to withdraw their investments whenever required. High liquid ratio indicates the ability to meet the liquid liabilities of the bank. Table 4 shows that both the liquid ratio of the Bandhan Bank i.e. Current Ratio and Quick Ratio. It is noticed that Quick Ratio is comparatively stable but the Current Ratio is significantly increase from 0.01% in 2015-16 to 0.09% in 2022-23 which indicated that the bank's liquidity position is satisfactory to meets its current financial obligations.

VII. FINDINGS

The main findings of the study are as follow

- Gross NPA Ratio climbed from 0.15% to 4.87% which shows a consistent upward trend. Huge amount of fund blocked as Gross NPA from the period of 2020-21 to 2022-23, however there is no time frame and meaningful follow up to get the blocked amount back which was quite alarming for the new established bank.
- A moderate degree of positive correlation between Net Profit and Net NPA was observed,

which indicated it adversely affects the profitability and financial health of the bank.

- Capital Adequacy Ratio of the bank significantly decreasing over the period of the study i.e. from 29.01% to 19.76%. It is quite alarming of the bank's financial health and stability.
- Management competency is also very fluctuating and disproportionately decreased over the period of 2015-16 to 2022-23.
- Earnings efficiency ratios significantly disproportionately decreasing over the period of the study which indicates Bank's financial performance is deteriorating.
- Liquidity position of the bank is satisfactory to meets its current financial obligations.

VIII. CONCLUSION

A good and expertise banking system paves the way for the overall development of the country by rapidly influencing the economic development of any country. But the biggest obstacle to this good and efficient banking system and development is the ever increasing NPAs. This problem is also evident in the newly born Bandhan Bank. Since Bandhan Bank started its working as an NGO with small stakeholders and marginalized people, priority sector should be given priority to giving advance and to recover that advance adequate and proper measures should be taken. As Bandhan Bank is young and lack experience, there is a lack of management skills in the initial journey which should be filled later. Since Bandhan Bank is a newly born bank, it has gone through a period like the Covid-19 pandemic, so even if it now faces some unwanted difficulties, it will definitely do well in the long run if these initial problems can be overcome.

IX. REFERENCES

Journals

- [1] Basu, S., Dutta, S., & Sarkar, A. "Bandhan: Can it Replicate Its Microfinance Success?", *Economic & Political Weekly*, Vol 50, Issue 35, pp.13-15, 2015.
- [2] Thomas, S. & Dave, G.B. "A Successful Microfinance to Bank: A Case Study of Bandhan", *International journal of science Technology and Management*, Vol. 4 Special Issue 1, pp. 513-522, 2015.
- [3] Mustafa, M. S. M. and Taqi, M. "A Study on the Financial Performance Evaluation of Punjab National Bank", *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp.5-15, 2017.
- [4] Nayek, S. "Analysing the Sustainability of Private Institutions Contributing towards Financial Inclusion: The Case Study of Bandhan Bank", *International Journal of Banking, Risk and Insurance*, Vol. 5, Issue 1, pp.24-32, 2017.
- [5] Agarwal, R. "An Analysis of Financial Performance of Select Nationalised Banks through CAMEL Model", *Research Review International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, Vol. 3, Issue 3, pp. 951-959, 2019.

Websites

- [1] <http://www.rbi.org.in>
- [2] <http://www.dbie.rbi.org.in>
- [3] <http://www.bandhanbank.com>
- [4] <http://www.moneycontrol.com>